

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OMODO****FIRST NAME: DANIEL MCMONDO****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULIMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Writing a good essay (EUCLID 2024, 6-12).
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2024, 15).
3. American Vs British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32).
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39).
5. Style guide, and why should I need on? (EUCLID 2024, 40).

WRITING A GOOD ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

I was excited to commence my Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Climate Change and Sustainability. It started with knowing more about EUCLID University and the different courses offered. I then selected the Climate Change and Sustainability PhD program, followed by registration for the course. I then familiarized myself with the course materials for the first course (ACA-401/ACA-401D). I studied the first course map and then accessed the two course platforms: the Course Management System (CMS) and the Learning Management System (LMS). The overview of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course checklist was very informative. I then reviewed the steps for writing, using Grammarly premium, sending a response paper and quiz, and contacting the course instructor.

Starting the Ph.D. was challenging in some ways. The first challenge was balancing work with study, especially during busy work periods and while for fieldwork in remote areas with limited internet connectivity. The second challenge was using Zotero, which took me some time to grasp. I had to review the course materials and other video clips on YouTube to understand how Zotero worked before I could start using it.

Through the first course, I learned about punctuation marks, their usage, and differentiating between correct and incorrect punctuation. Another exciting lesson was the difference between American and British English, plagiarism, styles, and using different Latin expressions.

2) A WELL-WRITTEN ACADEMIC ESSAY

From the first course, I understood that though there were many types of essays, this course focused on academic writing.

Scholarly writing was defined as nonfictional writing that is produced as part of academic work, for example, research findings on empirical work which may or may not be published, journals, books, newspapers, periodicals, monographs, conference papers, literature reviews, explication, technical report, translation and or students' presentation. I also noted that all academic writing involves formal prose registers, citations and references, and rhetorical moves to define project scope and position in relevant research and advance new contributions. All academic essays seek to answer hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence (EUCLID 2024, 7).

I learned that starting an essay requires starting early to have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write. It requires defining the question, analyzing the task, and presenting answers. It also requires drafting an initial plan that includes initial thoughts and ideas about a research topic to constitute a preliminary essay plan that helps to guide one's research work. I understood that underlining and highlighting relevant information during initial reading was helpful, while rereading and taking notes were essential steps forming the essay's basis (EUCLID 2024, 7).

I noted that the basic steps in writing an essay according to EUCLID (2024) include:

- Analyzing the question and defining key terms.
- Establishing the points of view.
- Researching the topic by using credible academic sources.
- Take notes from your preliminary reading.
- Develop your essay plan and organize your ideas.
- Drafting the essay into main parts, including the introduction, body, and conclusion.

Before handing in or submitting the essay, it is essential to keep the draft away for 1-2 days, review it and make changes, edit and redraft the essay, have a colleague or friend read it, and complete or check your references.

a) Researching the topic

EUCLID (2024, 8) stated that after understanding the topic, it is essential to read and research what to write as this gives the knowledge and evidence to develop a thesis and answer. While reading the topic, I understood it was necessary to answer the following questions. First, what do you already know about the subject? Second, what do you need to read and learn to write the essay? Third, Is this valuable material to your topic or argument? Lastly, can you use that material to support your answer? (EUCLID 2024, 8).

I learned from the first course that while reading, it was important always to keep the topic or question of the essay clearly in mind, use sound evidence to support one's argument, spend much time looking for relevant information, including summaries, direct quotes from texts, examples, case studies or statistics. I also learned that it was necessary to review different information sources while taking notes and include copying the bibliographic details of everything one reads, including the author's name, date, title, publisher, place of publishing, and other relevant details notes (EUCLID 2024, 9).

Reading lists: EUCLID (2024, 9) also highlighted that I consult as many as possible, locate relevant material in the library, and use the catalog to perform topic and subject searches based on a list of suggested readings. Once you have your reading, use a table of contents and index to find relevant material, skim through the text to locate specific information, and when you find something you need, read closely and flag the pages with post-it notes so you can return for close reading.

Thinking it through: I noted that essay writing requires creative and critical thinking. Creative thinking encourages you to broaden your ideas using brainstorming or mind-mapping techniques. In contrast, critical thinking encourages you to narrow the focus or scope of your ideas by asking why an example is essential to your argument. Keep the essay balanced. That is, include information from different authors, remembering not only to include evidence that agrees with your opinion but also examine different or opposing views, including evaluating the various arguments – explain why one argument is more convincing than another and how they relate to the conclusion your essay arrives at (EUCLID 2024, 9).

b) Organizing your ideas

I also learned that writing an essay plan is essential to help you determine how to answer the question and how I should structure it after reading and researching. A plan should consider first deciding a possible answer to the question, secondly, selecting the information you will use to answer the question, thirdly, looking through your notes and choosing examples to provide evidence to support your answer, and then deciding which points you will discuss in which order before writing all in a sketch to form your essay plan (EUCLID 2024, 9).

c) Writing the essay

I noted that the first step in writing an essay is to produce the first draft according to a structure and framework of the essay, which is like the raw material you refine through editing and redrafting. The structure of the essay should follow the format starting with an introduction, then a body, and finally a conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 10).

i) *Introduction*

I understood from (EUCLID 2024, 10) that the introduction moves from general to specific, opening with a short orientation of a sentence or two, answering the question with a thesis statement, and providing a summary or road map of the essay, ensuring keep it brief but mentioning all the main ideas.

ii) *Body*

The essay consists of paragraphs, each building block in constructing one's argument. It is where first you answer the question by developing a discussion, then show your knowledge and grasp of the material you read, offering exposition and evidence to build your argument and using relevant examples and quotes, structuring the body into sections that deal with each part of the question (EUCLID 2024, 10).

iii) *Conclusion*

I noted the conclusion moves from specific to general, restating one's answer to the question, re-summarizing the main points, and including a final, broad statement about possible implications and future directions for research to qualify the conclusion, remembering not to introduce any new information in the conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 10).

3) PUNCTUATION

Britannica describes punctuation as 'the use of spacing, conventional signs, and specific typographical devices as aids to understanding and correctly reading handwritten and printed texts, both silently and aloud. Punctuation derives from the Latin punctus or point' I learned that 'plagiarism is unethical and wrong; it is unfair to use someone's work and not give them credit, and it is a serious academic offense with severe consequences.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

I learned that that American English was the dominant influence on "world English" (cf British English) mainly due to the population of the US vs. UK, the wealth of the US economy vs the UK, and influences, the magnitude of higher education in America

vs. the UK, the magnitude of the publishing industry in America, Magnitude of global mass media and technology influence, the international political and economic position of the US (EUCLID 2024, 25).

I also learned further that the general categories of difference between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE), namely, different pronunciations but the exact spelling, for example, advertisement, different spelling, same pronunciation, for example, Axe – ax and color – color; same term, different but similar spelling and pronunciation for example Aluminium Vs. Aluminum, Polythene Vs. Polyethylene; same words but different or additional meanings; grammar, syntax; differences in usage with SBE Large collective nouns among others (EUCLID 2024, 25).

5) PLAGIARISM

The most exciting topic that I learned from this course is plagiarism. According to EUCLID (2024, 34), plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. Britannica also defines plagiarism as the use of spacing, conventional signs, and specific typographical devices to aid in understanding and correctly reading handwritten and printed texts silently and aloud.

I also learned that the solution to avoid plagiarism is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using and that there are two things about citing – in-text citations and list of works cited” (EUCLID 2024, 34).

I noted that in mentioning the source for a long quote, which is more than four lines long, you indent the quotation without putting quotation marks (EUCLID 2024, 35).

I must testify that before undertaking this course, I knew little about plagiarism and its negative consequences on a publication. Sometimes, I could copy and paste information from the Internet and Artificial Intelligence. Still, the course enhanced my understanding of plagiarism and taught me how to avoid it as much as possible in the future.

6) STYLE GUIDE

I noted that EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian), but other internationally recognized Rules are acceptable. In addition, I learned that EUCLID recommends using American English, though both English versions were accepted (EUCLID 2024, 41).

EUCLID (2024, 41) defined a Style as “a means of documenting a writer’s approach to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent.” It further states, “Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting.” EUCLID (2024, 41) states, “There is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent.” and that “so guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to contribute while ensuring that the

finished piece does not necessarily carry the personal style of the writer but that of the publication, company, or website associated with the writing.

I found that the EUCLID templates and guidelines for information on how to format response papers were user-friendly, had the recommended writing style embedded, and guided me while writing this response paper

7) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I found the first course (ACA-401D) for my Ph.D. in climate change and sustainability on scholarly writing beneficial as this skill is fundamental to successfully undertaking such an academic program.

I learned essential topics like how to write a good essay, including researching the topic, organizing your ideas and the actual writing, starting with an introduction, body and conclusion, punctuation, plagiarism, and style guide, among other essential aspects.

These skills have set me on the right footing to effectively and efficiently undertake subsequent courses required to complete my Ph.D. in Climate change and sustainability at EUCLID University.

REFERENCES

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